

Varying efficacy of different species-specific insulins in rats.

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Introduction:

Both our previous research and already published studies suggest a varied efficacy of species-specific (rat, human, porcine) insulins in lowering blood glucose levels in rodent models. The rat insulin seems to be more compatible, eliciting a more robust response in target tissues compared to human or porcine insulins in rodents. We tested the sensitivity of the Insulin Tolerance Test (ITT) in detecting varying effectiveness among different types of insulin (rat/human) in rats.

Methods:

Male Brown Norway rats (270-300g) were included in experimental groups.

ITT: To identify an appropriate insulin dosage that emphasizes differences among various insulins, we tested doses of 160, 80, 40 and 20 µg/kg.

Human recombinant insulin and rat insulin (INS1+INS2) was used in dose 20 µg/kg (0,5 IU/kg). Insulin was administered intravenously and blood glucose levels were measured from a drop of blood obtained from the tail vein using a glucometer at baseline and at 10, 20, 30, 40, 50, 60, 70, 80, 100 and 120 min after insulin injection. The decline in blood glucose levels was recalculated using the area under the curve method, applying the trapezium rule.

Results:

Optimal dosage for detecting differences in glucose-lowering ability of insulin in Brown Norway rats was 20 µg/kg.

Brown Norway rats exhibited higher sensitivity to mixture of rat insulins if compared to human insulin (AUC of glucose 79,4856 vs 103,36135 (% basal). h).

Conclusions:

Our results suggest that equal mixture of rat species-specific insulins (INS1 + INS2) is more effective in lowering blood glucose levels than human insulin, in Brown Norway rats.

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